

Identifying the Role of Teachers in Developing Entrepreneurial Intention of Prospective Teachers

- Saubia Ramzan** Professor, Institute of Management Sciences, University of Balochistan, Balochistan, Pakistan. Email: saubia7@yahoo.com
- Muhammad Shakir** Lecturer, Department of Educational Training, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan.
- Jam Muhammad Zafar** Assistant Professor, Department of Teacher Education, Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan.

Abstract

This research study identified the main areas related to entrepreneurship teacher education. The main objectives of the study were: (a) to identify the importance of entrepreneurship education for teacher education in Pakistan; (b) to identify the areas to prepare pre-service teachers for entrepreneurship education. The nature of study was descriptive while mixed method approach was used to gather information. Twelve teacher educators and eighty five prospective teachers were selected by using convenience sampling technique. ENVIVO-11 and SPSS were used to analyze qualitative and quantitative data. It was revealed that mostly interviewees agreed on entrepreneurial education should be made a part of national professional standards of teachers. Majority of the trainee teachers appreciated entrepreneurship education. Most of the respondents intervene about imparting and improving entrepreneurial education for prospective teachers' course. Interviewees are appreciating this step of entrepreneurial intentions in prospective teachers' course.

Key Words

Entrepreneurship, teacher education, prospective teachers, professional standard.

Introduction

Entrepreneurial mindset is becoming the part of every policy across the globe. The previous research studies show the significant role that education and training play in the development of such mindsets (Thurik & Wennekers, 2004). Teachers are considered the monuments of this change, therefore, it is the basic demand of teaching profession that teachers must be equipped with the right knowledge, skills and attitude to enable to inculcate new curricula, modern andragogical skills and learning environment that they will need to acquire entrepreneurial skills and competencies (Nazri, Aroosha, & Omar).

Prospective teachers/students are playing significant role in entrepreneurial education. Their own learning process, interest, motivation, inner drive, initiative, innovation and critical reflection are improving day by day. Learning environment is known as a gateway and teachers act as change agents for imparting entrepreneurial intention in prospective teachers/students. Positive environment of institutions and support would help prospective teachers/ to get various tangible (finance, know-how, etc.) and intangible (motivation, self-confidence, awareness of related regulation) resources and skills about entrepreneurship (Trivedi, 2016).

Introduction of entrepreneurial education at school, college or university level is associated with changes in educational design, strategies, teaching practice and training of professional teachers. Teachers are also considered to be the most influential actors in education. Teachers' character in class room for shaping the students' learning environment heavily associated with their views, knowledge, philosophies, perceptions and attitudes (Elbaz, 2018). Therefore, developed countries also have professional standards for teachers so that maximum results of change could be achieved. As professional standards of teachers and its implementations are demands of the day; it is also need of the future to add one standard of entrepreneurial education in it. In this way; we may build entrepreneurial intention in prospective teacher/students because they are professional teachers of the future. It will also help to decrease unemployment rate and increase economic situation of the country by opening up new business opportunities.

Now a day, Higher Education Educations (HEIs) are imparting their positive role to developing entrepreneurial intention among potential entrepreneurs (Fayolle, 2013). Entrepreneurial education in Greenberg, McKone-Sweet, and Wilson (2011) were of the view that Entrepreneurial education

in universities develop entrepreneurial skills among the individual that contribute to enhance the new business opportunities. Maritz and Brown (2013) expressed that entrepreneurial education there are some agreement about basic issues such as what are the major outcomes needed, what the main instructional strategies, andragogical and pedagogies are how impact factors for assessment are defined.

Pakistan is one of the developing countries that ranked at 138th in 189 countries on the level of ease of doing business (Nichter & Goldmark, 2009). According to the Qureshi and Mian (2012) report, the emerging entrepreneurial activity reported at lowest level in Pakistan. Overall businesses are run on very small scales as compared to other regional counterparts.

In Pakistan educational institutes lacks entrepreneurial learning. Majority of students from these institutes do not have critical thinking, problem solving, risk taking tendency and self-efficacy abilities. There is no teacher training institute that offers courses on entrepreneurship except one or two courses in Business Administration degree programs. There is a huge demand to promote a culture of entrepreneurship in students and faculty to overcome the socioeconomic crisis in Pakistan institutions (Abbasi, Malik, Chaudhry, & Imdadullah, 2011). The youth of Pakistan has huge potential which can be utilized to develop perspective entrepreneur teacher in terms of provision of real time knowledge about creativity, innovation, and handling uncertainty however entrepreneurial educational contents are limited to faculty only. There is need to develop entrepreneurs employees for the effective exploitation of human resources through incorporating entrepreneurial education in management education. It will benefit the economic growth of Pakistan through consistency and sustainability along with positive socioeconomic outcomes (Karlan & Valdivia, 2011).

Entrepreneurial educators are using chronological and script writing approach of motivation, arrangement, and pupil's promotion according to their abilities (Cuban, 1986). There are large number of approaches, trainings and programs on the exploration of opportunities (Fiet & Patel, 2008). According to the needs of world, we are always searching for new opportunities, and for this we are more focusing on entrepreneurial decisions, experts role script, hierarchy, and plans, which are helpful in constructing entrepreneurial methods. So the conclusion is, there is large number of entrepreneurs (Sarasvathy, 2001). Which describes the challenges of entrepreneurial world, and the time is to focus on these challenges and find out the exact one for creating connection between the diversity of entrepreneurial motivation and desired outcomes. Entrepreneurial culture is developing world wide. For example, European Union made different strategies for enhancing the entrepreneurial skills and perceptions in choosing career (Sarasvathy, 2001).

Influential and stakeholders' support and overall governance structure are reflected poor conditions in Pakistan. If the plan is to stimulate entrepreneurship and skills development creativities, there is a great need for institutional and stakeholders' support contrivance (Shabbir, Shariff, Kiran, Faisal, & Shahzad, 2016).

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are: (a) to identify the importance of entrepreneurship education for teacher education in Pakistan; (b) to identify the need and areas to prepare pre-service and in-service teachers for entrepreneurship education; and (c) to develop effective teacher education systems for entrepreneurship.

Research Method

The purpose of this study is to measure the role of teachers in developing entrepreneurial intention of prospective teachers/students. This study was descriptive in nature based on survey research. All the teachers and prospective teachers/students of public institutions in southern Punjab were the population of the study who were enrolled in BS (Hons), B.Ed (Hons) and B.Ed 1.5 year courses which assisted in achieving the research objectives. Based on convenience sampling techniques researcher had selected (06) six public institutions of southern Punjab, (02) teacher educators for interview from each institution and (15) fifteen prospective teachers from each institution were selected.

Questionnaire and interview protocol were used to gather information from the respondents. Twenty-eight statements of entrepreneurial intention from entrepreneurial aptitude selected. Pilot tested results showed the reliability coefficient for overall scale was 0.92. For qualitative data an interview protocol was developed in light of review literature and expert opinions.

Analysis of Data

After collecting the data from the prospective teachers and teacher educators, data were fed in SPSS-20 by using certain formula's i.e. mean and percentage to find out the entrepreneurial intention of prospective teachers/students. NVIVO-11 software was used for qualitative data analysis. First audio interview of twelve respondents were added as English transcript form on the word file by the name of each interviewee. These file transport into NVIVO-11.

Word query analysis was applied for possible responses of the results. The results were shown in tree map and word cloud as under:

Job opportunity for Prospective Teachers

Word tree map provide a clear concept about job opportunities for prospective teachers/students after their graduation. It showed that they have limited access of job after graduation. Their families live in societies where resources of earning are also limited. Prospective teachers' degrees are acceptable in the field of education. In education sector, job opportunities are very difficult; therefore, unemployment rate is high in this field of graduation. Prospective graduates are worried about this difficult situation of unemployment.

Effect of Entrepreneurial Education

This word cloud indicated that entrepreneurial education can provide motivation to prospective teachers/students in future. Mostly interviewee agreed that first they need to promote their expertise and knowledge so that they may be able to understand business and stimulate it further in their students.

Suggestions for Improving Entrepreneurial Education

This word cloud provides suggestions that how we can improve entrepreneurial education and intention in prospective teachers/students. This word cloud theme is indicating in table form of words ranking and percentage as;

Table 1. Word Ranking and Percentage about Suggestions for Improving Entrepreneurial Education

S.No	Word	Length	Count	Weighted	Percentage (%)	Similar Words
1	business	8	22		8.40	Business
2	study	5	19		6.87	field, learning, study, subject
3	start	5	13		4.96	Start
4	become	6	12		4.58	Become
5	employ	6	12		4.58	Employ
6	graduation	10	12		4.58	Graduation
7	instead	7	12		4.58	Instead
8	prospective	11	12		4.58	Prospective
9	teachers	8	12		4.58	Teachers
10	criteria	8	12		4.58	Criteria
11	developed	9	6		2.29	developed, development, education
12	experience	10	5		1.91	Experience
13	market	6	5		1.91	Market
14	courses	7	4		1.53	course, courses
15	appropriate	11	3		1.15	Appropriate
16	demand	6	4		1.15	demand, required
17	financial	9	3		1.15	Financial
18	intentions	10	3		1.15	intention, intentions
19	knowledge	9	4		1.15	knowledge, learning
20	necessary	9	4		1.15	necessary, required
21	sports	6	3		1.15	Sports
22	awareness	9	2		0.76	Awareness
23	basics	6	2		0.76	Basics
24	confidence	10	2		0.76	Confidence
25	critical	8	2		0.76	Critical
26	entrepreneurial	15	2		0.76	Entrepreneurial
27	improved	8	2		0.76	Improved
28	professional	12	2		0.76	Professional

This Table 1 illustrates interviewee suggestions about imparting and improving entrepreneurial education for prospective teachers/students' course. Interviewees are appreciating this step of entrepreneurial intentions in prospective teachers' course. They suggested that criteria for prospective teachers should be developed that can increase their experience in the field of business. Appropriate courses should be started that cover the demand of their financial intentions. Knowledge, necessary financial support, awareness, confidence and critical thinking can improve the entrepreneurial profession of these prospective teachers

Role of Teachers in Developing Entrepreneurial Intention

This word tree map provides clear concept about the role of teachers in developing entrepreneurial intention of prospective teachers/students. Teachers are central part of all strategies, implementation, motivations and developing entrepreneurial intention of prospective teachers. This word tree map also reflect detail and strategies that what and how a teacher play active role in developing entrepreneurial intentions of prospective teachers. Map clearly depicts that six ideas come from the tree map. First, prospective teachers can play active role in developing motivation after their graduation. Second, for this purpose entrepreneurial education make the part of their course and facilitate them. Third, for this purpose trained teachers should be appointed. Appropriate training, workshops and complete facilitation should convey to instructors (teachers) so that they should be able to teach entrepreneurship courses properly. Fourth, suggestions favored that entrepreneurial education should be made as important part of national professional standards of teachers. Fifth, prospective teachers have limited resources of earning. This step will increase the standard of teachers. Sixth, entrepreneurial education is a good step for future and great opportunity of earnings for prospective teachers. It will increase entrepreneurial intentions of prospective teachers and business culture.

Entrepreneurial Education and Professional Standards

This word cloud illustrate the suggestions of interviewees that; if entrepreneurial education be made as the part of national professional standards of teachers, it will definitely accumulate and increase the business culture and economic situation of the country. It can improve the progress and condition of the nations.

Table 2. Students' Ideas about Self-Reliance

Sr. No.	Statement	Level of Agreement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I really want to learn and understand entrepreneurship program as much as possible	<i>f</i>	38	28	00	09	10
		%	44.7	32.9	00	1.06	11.8
2	I want to do better in my life than I have done before	<i>f</i>	09	36	07	25	08
		%	10.6	42.4	8.2	29.4	9.4
3	I want to learn something new on entrepreneurship program so I work as hard as I can do in this field	<i>f</i>	15	44	08	13	05
		%	17.6	51.8	9.4	15.3	5.9
4	When I am confronted with a problem, I can find various solutions of the problems.	<i>f</i>	29	38	00	13	05
		%	34.1	44.7	00	15.3	5.9
5	I set enough goals to maintain a clear sense of purpose.	<i>f</i>	49	24	06	04	02
		%	57.6	28.2	7.1	4.7	2.4
6	The failures provide opportunities for innovation	<i>f</i>	27	37	00	12	09
		%	31.8	43.5	00	14.1	10.6
7	When I fail to attain the targets, my first statement that it is due to teaching issue.	<i>f</i>	36	30	02	11	06
		%	42.4	35.3	2.4	12.9	7.1
8	I continuously try to make my activities reliable.	<i>f</i>	10	38	07	23	07
		%	11.8	44.7	8.2	27.1	8.2
9	I am sure that I can develop my organization through inculcating certain skills.	<i>f</i>	21	36	05	19	04
		%	24.7	42.4	5.9	22.4	4.7
10	Working hard is something I like doing	<i>f</i>	09	45	11	14	06
		%	10.6	52.9	12.9	16.5	7.1
	Average	<i>f</i>	243	356	46	155	62
		%	28.20	41.20	5.3	17.98	7.20

Note: Only most frequently used values are discussed in interpretation.

Table 2 demonstrates descriptive statistics of each statement relating to self-reliance for entrepreneurship program. About (45+33) 78% respondents stated that they really want to learn and understand entrepreneurship program as much as possible, nearly (11+42) 49% respondents specified that they want to do better in their life than they have done before, roundabout (18+52) 80% respondents want to learn something new on entrepreneurship program so that they work as hard as they can do in this field, almost (34+45) 89% respondents explained that when they are confronted with a problem, they can find various solutions of the problems, As (58+28) 86% respondents agreed that they set enough goals to maintain a clear sense of purpose. Approximately (32+43) 75% respondents illuminated that the failures provide opportunities for innovation, about (42+35) 77% respondents showed that when they fail to attain the targets, my first statement that it is due to teaching issue, almost (12+45) 57% respondents illustrated that they continuously try to make my activities reliable, around (25+42) 67% respondents stated that they develop their organization through inculcating certain skills, nearly (11+53) 64% respondents identified that working hard is something they like doing. As a whole (28+41) 68% respondents demonstrate inclination towards self-reliance for entrepreneurship programs.

Table 3. Students' Ideas about Work Intention

S. No.	Statement	Level of Agreement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I don't have concern what my friend think want to be entrepreneur.	<i>f</i> %	22 25.9	33 38.8	05 5.9	13 15.3	12 14.1
2	I am in favor of being independent rather than work for others.	<i>f</i> %	24 28.2	41 48.2	10 11.8	07 8.2	03 3.5
3	I can readily imagine new uses for old ideas.	<i>f</i> %	30 35.3	39 45.9	05 5.9	05 5.9	06 7.1
4	I encourage experimentation	<i>f</i> %	13 15.3	35 41.2	14 16.5	20 23.5	03 3.5
5	I am sure that increasing my teaching skills will be more beneficial.	<i>f</i> %	22 25.9	33 38.8	03 3.5	17 20.0	10 11.8
6	I accept change easily and become disappointed with the status quo	<i>f</i> %	19 22.4	34 40.0	08 9.4	13 15.3	11 12.9
7	I launch something new with available resources instead of waiting for ideal situation	<i>f</i> %	15 17.6	31 36.5	04 4.7	28 32.9	07 8.2
8	I have access on investment to start being an entrepreneur.	<i>f</i> %	24 28.2	40 47.1	02 2.4	10 11.8	09 10.6
9	I guess that risks are linked with business.	<i>f</i> %	17 20.0	48 56.5	07 8.2	11 12.9	02 2.4
10	A course on business would be useful.	<i>f</i> %	15 17.6	44 51.8	07 8.2	11 12.9	08 9.4
11	Working with my own business would be more respectable than working with others.	<i>f</i> %	14 16.5	53 62.4	07 8.2	08 9.4	03 3.5
	Average	<i>f</i> %	215 23.0	431 46.1	72 7.7	143 15.3	74 7.9

Note: Only most frequently used values are discussed in interpretation.

Table 3 shows descriptive statistics of each statement concerning to work intention for entrepreneurship program. Nearly (26+39) 65% respondents indicated that they don't have concern what my friend think want to be entrepreneur, nearly (28+48) 76% respondents identified that I am in favor of being independent rather than work for others, roundabout (35+46) 81% respondents can readily imagine new uses for old ideas, practically (15+41) 56% respondents encourage experimentation, About (22+40) 62% respondents embrace change easily and become dissatisfied with the status quo. Nearly (18+37) 55% respondents launch something new with available resources instead of waiting for ideal situation, about (28+47) 75% respondents have access on investment to start being an entrepreneur, almost (20+57) 77% respondents feel that the risks are linked with business, (18+52) 70% respondents stated that a course on business would be useful, nearly (17+62) 79% respondents identified that working with their own business than working with others. As a whole (23+46) 69% respondents demonstrate inclination towards work intention for entrepreneurship programs.

Table 4. Students' Ideas about Team Responsibilities

S. No.	Statement	Level of Agreement	SA	A	UC	DA	SDA
1	I am able to shift organizational system with less complaints	<i>f</i> %	36 42.4	32 37.6	05 5.9	03 3.5	09 10.6
2	My habit is to reach for help and acknowledge the assistance	<i>f</i> %	16 18.8	38 44.7	03 3.6	26 30.6	02 2.4
3	I like incentives to reinforce change	<i>f</i> %	10 11.8	37 43.5	09 10.6	22 25.9	07 8.2
4	I trust others rather than on my position to follow	<i>f</i>	20	39	03	16	07

	me.	%	23.5	45.9	3.5	18.8	8.2
5	I have always been connected with guider on regular basis.	f	24	38	04	14	05
		%	28.2	44.7	4.7	16.5	5.9
6	I feel satisfaction to help other in life.	f	17	32	09	25	02
		%	20.0	37.6	10.6	29.4	2.4
7	I am choosy about people professionally and academically.	f	18	39	04	19	05
		%	21.2	45.9	4.7	22.4	5.8
	Average	f	141	255	37	125	37
		%	23.7	42.9	6.2	21.0	6.2

Note: Only most frequently used values are discussed in interpretation.

Table 4 reveals descriptive statistics of each statement relating to team responsibilities for entrepreneurship program. Almost (42+38) 80% respondents indicated that they are able to shift organizational mechanisms with minimal complaints, approximately (19+45) 64% respondents agreed that their habit is to reach for help and acknowledge the assistance, about (12+44) 56% respondents like incentives to reinforce change, nearly (24+46) 70% respondents explained that they rely on their relationships with others rather than on their position to follow them or do what they want, Equally (28+45) 73% respondents approved that they are always in contact with experts and mentors for key areas of their life on regular basis, Approximately (20+38) 58% respondents feel great personal satisfaction in helping other people, roundabout (21+46) 67% respondents showed that they are strategic and highly selective about people who are close to them personally and professionally. As a whole (24+43) 67% respondents demonstrate inclination towards team responsibilities for entrepreneurship programs.

Conclusions and Discussion

In the present research we tried to discuss the observed data about role of teachers in developing entrepreneurial intention of prospective teachers. This research is both qualitative as well as quantitative. It is first inclusive study covering the basis of entrepreneurial intention among prospective teachers. Young generation, especially prospective teachers of higher education institutions need to play a role in accomplishing government initiatives to foster entrepreneurship culture in Pakistan. They must have a comprehensive understanding of the idea before applying and creating enterprises. Generally, entrepreneurial intention in research mostly examined from the behavioral features towards career. The entrepreneurial intention plays an important role in deciding students' aspirations that are measured through their confidence and capability to set sustainable vision for the entrepreneurial activities that they pursue. The determination and success of prospective teachers of higher education institutions are influenced by their level of intention.

The analysis of the data reveals many important findings and discovers developmental steps for further progress in the concerned area. The result of word tree map showed that prospective teachers have limited resources of job after their graduation because their degrees are acceptable in the field of education. Their families live in societies where resources of earnings are also limited. Therefore, unemployment rate is high in this field of graduation. Prospective graduates are worried about this difficult situation of unemployment. Current study word cloud results showed that entrepreneurial education can provide motivation to prospective teachers/students in future. Mostly interviewee agreed that first promote their expertise and knowledge so that they become able to understand business and stimulate it in their students. Interviewees are appreciating entrepreneurial intentions in prospective teachers' course. They suggested that criteria for prospective teachers should be developed that increase their experience in the field of business. Appropriate courses should be start which covers the demand of their financial intentions. According to interviewees; by the knowledge, necessary financial sports, awareness, confidence and critical thinking, entrepreneurial intentions can be increased.

The word tree map results provide a concept about the role of teachers in developing entrepreneurial intention of prospective teachers. Main ideas of the tree map showed that prospective teachers can play active role in developing motivation after their graduation. For this purpose entrepreneurial education make the part of their course and facilitate them, trained teachers should be appointed, suitable training, workshops and full facilitation should convey to instructors (teachers) so that they should teach entrepreneurship courses properly because teachers are central part of all strategies, implementation, motivations and developing entrepreneurial intention of prospective teachers. They suggested that entrepreneurial education should be made a part of national professional standards of teachers. This step will enhance the standard of teachers. Entrepreneurial education is a great opportunity of earning for prospective teachers in future. It will increase entrepreneurial intentions of prospective teachers and business culture. (Souitaris, Zerbiniati, & Al-Laham, 2007) also concluded a relationship between

entrepreneurial education and the effect on intention, the most influential benefits of entrepreneurial education is the rise of attitudes, entrepreneurial intention and inspiration.

Word cloud results illustrate the suggestions of interviewees that if entrepreneurial education should be made a part of national professional standards of teachers, it will definitely be accumulated and increase the business culture and economic situation of the country. It can improve the progress and condition of the nations.

For quantitative data a questionnaire was used to measure entrepreneurial intentions in prospective teachers. Entrepreneurial intention was analyzed by its three factor named; self-reliance, work intention and team responsibilities. Descriptive statistics of each statement relating to self-reliance for entrepreneurship program demonstrated that about seventy eight percent respondents really want to learn and understand entrepreneurship program as much as possible, nearly forty nine respondents want to do better in their lives than they have done before. As a whole sixty eight percent respondents demonstrate inclination towards self-reliance for entrepreneurship programs. Present study results indicated work intention in prospective teachers for entrepreneurship program. Practically fifty six percent respondents encourage experimentation. As a whole sixty nine percent respondents demonstrate inclination towards work intention for entrepreneurship programs. Descriptive statistics of present study relating to entrepreneurship program showed that almost eighty percent respondents indicated that they are able to shift organizational mechanisms with minimal complaints. Approximately sixty four percent respondents agreed that their habit is to reach for help and acknowledge the assistance, as a whole sixty seven percent respondents demonstrate inclination towards team responsibilities for entrepreneurship programs.

Recommendations

After study results it is recommended that

1. Courses on entrepreneurship education should be introduced in pre-service teacher education program.
2. Proper training of in-service teachers for entrepreneurial education may be arranged.
3. Government may take initiatives to include at least one standard on entrepreneurial education in professional teaching standards.

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